

SYNTHESIS OF 4-QUINAZOLOLS. PART I

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Three substituted 4-quinazolols have been prepared with a view to testing them for analgesic properties.

The search for synthetic analgesics, based on the partial structures of morphine, has led to several investigations in recent years (Kirkpatrick and Parkar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1123; Cassaday and Bogert, *ibid.*, 1939, 61, 3055; Schaumann, *Arch. exp. Path. Pharm.*, 1940, 196, 104; Harnest and Burger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 370; Cook and Read, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 399; Anker, Cook and Heilbron, *ibid.*, 1945, 917; Anker and Cook, *ibid.*, 1946, 58). The most comprehensive work in this direction has been carried out by Lee *et al.*, Barel Jubilee Volume, Basle, 1946, pp. 264-305), and the synthesis of the compounds containing partial morphine structures has been exhaustively studied. They have divided these compounds into the following four types :

Compounds of type II were obtained by the action of Grignard reagents on N-alkyl γ -piperidones. It may be recalled that the present authors have been independently carrying out similar syntheses with substituted N-alkyl γ -piperidones, obtained by the Mannich reaction (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 293; 1948, 25, 433).

With a view to studying the effect of other heterocyclic rings with analgesic activity, the reaction has been extended to 4-quinazolones which have been treated with alkyl or aryl magnesium halides to give the substituted 4-quinazolols :

* II-R = -C₆H₅; III-R = -CH₂.CH₂.CH₃; IV-R = -CH₂.CH₂.CH₂.CH₃

2-Methyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I), required for these reactions, was prepared by the method of Grimmel, Guenther and Morgan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 543). It may be mentioned that only very few hydroxy derivatives of quinazolines have so far been reported in literature.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methyl-3 : 4-diphenyl-4-quinazolol (II).—The Grignard reagent was obtained in the usual manner from magnesium (1.2 g., 0.05 mole) and 7.9 g. (0.05 mole) of bromobenzene in 50 c.c. of dry ether in an atmosphere of nitrogen in a three-necked flask, fitted with a dropping funnel, a reflux condenser and a mechanical stirrer. When the magnesium had gone into solution, the flask was cooled in ice and salt and 11.8 g. (0.05 mole) of 2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolone (I), suspended in 100 c.c. dry benzene, were rapidly added. The ice-bath was removed after 15 minutes and the mixture refluxed for five hours after which it was poured over crushed ice and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated quinazolol was collected at the pump, washed with a little cold water, dried and recrystallised from boiling ethyl alcohol in white crystals, m.p. 258-60°, yield 7.5 g. (I) is also soluble in hot water. (Found: N, 9.15. $C_{21}H_{18}ON_2$ requires N, 8.95 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-phenyl-4-n-propyl-4-quinazolol was obtained as above by the addition of *n*-propylmagnesium bromide (prepared from 0.3 g. magnesium and 1.6 g. *n*-propyl bromide in 25 c.c. dry ether) on 3 g. of the quinazolone (I), suspended in 30 c.c. of dry benzene. It was recrystallised from boiling ethyl alcohol in white crystals, m.p. 262-65°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: N, 9.6. $C_{18}H_{20}ON_2$ requires N, 10.00 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-phenyl-4-n-butyl-4-quinazolol was obtained as above by the action of *n*-butylmagnesium bromide (prepared from 0.3 g. magnesium and 1.6 g. of *n*-butyl bromide in 25 c.c. dry ether) on 3 g. of the quinazolone (I), suspended in 30 c.c. of dry benzene. It was recrystallised from boiling ethyl alcohol, m.p. 272°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: N, 9.21. $C_{19}H_{22}ON_2$ requires N, 9.52 per cent).